

PRACTICAL EXERCISES IN THE CLASSROOM OF SCIENCE LESSONS IN A SCHOOL FOR CHILDREN WITH HEARING IMPAIRMENT

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Annotatsiya: This article describes the application procedure of practical exercises used in the classroom in the school for children with hearing impairments and the features of skills developed in children with hearing impairments through these practical exercises.

Key words: Sensation, perception, experience, property, animate nature, inanimate nature, purpose, observation, experimental field, flora, fauna.

In a school for children with hearing impairments, hands-on activities are used in the classroom, which gives students the opportunity to take in what they are learning with several senses, that is, they can not only see the object, but also feel it. they conduct various experiments on it, they test its properties (for example, by counting, hammering, fragility of things, by bending - elasticity, flexibility, etc.). inanimate natural objects (stones, beneficial insects, plants and their parts, small animals, etc.) are used.

Practical work is carried out in the following order:

- announcing the purpose of work;
- the teacher gives directions;
- explanation of the task;
- distribution of materials;
- monitoring;
- explanation-interview of the results of the work;
- write the conclusions in a notebook;
- draw pictures;

During practical work, the teacher helps some students when the task seems unclear or complicated. If necessary, it is necessary to repeatedly explain the content of the work to the whole class. The main difficulty of practical work is to understand observed phenomena, distinguish the most important ones, and be able to express conclusions.

Practical training in the field of living nature is related to long-term observation and experiments. In a lesson devoted to practical work in a branch of living nature, its purpose and consistency of execution should be explained.

Questionnaires can be given to students with hearing impairment. The results of the work in the nature corner are used when studying relevant topics.

Practical work on the cultivation of plants in the front yard of the school expands and deepens the knowledge received in the classroom lessons, arouses interest in nature and agricultural work.

The practical work in the front of the school and the discussion and the teacher's explanations related to them and the observations of the students should be conducted as an outdoor lesson during the class hours. The lesson is divided into theoretical and practical parts.

In the theoretical part of the lesson, the teacher explains the importance and essence of the work in front of him, introduces students with hearing impairments to the plants that should be studied by means of work tools and working methods.

When planning this part of the lesson, it is necessary to clearly define the knowledge that students with hearing impairments will acquire and master in science. Explaining the purpose and importance of the work, the teacher shows the children the correct methods of doing it and says why it should be done this way and not otherwise. Then the teacher asks one or two students to do the work and only when they can do it correctly, he allows the whole class to start working.

The second part of the lesson is children's practical work.

During the practical work, the teacher monitors the students with hearing impairment, provides additional explanations, evaluates the quality of the work, highlights the good ones, and offers to eliminate the mistakes made.

The end of the lesson is concluded with a conversation, and the lesson determines what new information the children learned, what they learned to do, how they behaved during the work. will provide information on how to organize this work.

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